

Evaluation of Differences in Media Consumption in Oredo Local Government, Edo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study evaluated media consumption patterns in Oredo Local Government Area, Edo State, focusing on how media shapes public perceptions and behaviours. Anchored on the uses and gratifications theory, it explored how media consumption satisfies audience needs and influences social and political engagement. A descriptive survey research design was used to collect data from 384 respondents out of a population of 553,300. The findings revealed significant exposure to various media platforms, impacting civic engagement and social awareness. The researchers concluded that targeted media strategies are needed to engage underserved communities and enhance media credibility through transparency and local involvement. Recommendations include government and telecommunication companies to work towards reducing internet cost and expanding broadband coverage to make digital media more accessible to a Wilder population.

Keywords: Media Consumption, Local Government, Digital Media, Social Awareness

Introduction

The way people consume media has changed a lot over the years. In the past, traditional media like newspapers, radio and television were the main sources of news and entertainment. However, the rise of digital media has changed this. More people now use online platforms, streaming services, and social media to access content. This shift has created clear differences in how people of different ages, locations and backgrounds use media (McQuail, 2010). According to Offcom (2020), media consumption refers to the ways in which people access and engage with different types of media content. This includes reading newspapers, watching television, listening to the radio, browsing the internet and using social media. It also covers newer forms of digital engagement, such as streaming videos, podcasts, and online gaming. It is influenced by various factors, including age, location, income level, education and personal interests. For example, younger people tend to prefer digital platforms like YouTube and TikTok, while older generations may rely more on traditional media such as newspapers and television.

Statista (2022) states one major reason for the evolution in media consumption in today's digital-driven world is technology. Many people now prefer digital media because it is faster, cheaper and more interactive. Media consumers believe that newspapers have lost many readers because people can now read news online for free. Similarly, radio is facing competition from podcasts and music streaming services that allow users to choose what they want to listen to. Television is also struggling because more people prefer watching content on streaming platforms like Netflix and YouTube (Statista, 2022).

Furthermore, studies have shown that younger people prefer digital media, while older people still rely on traditional media like television and radio. This difference in media consumption means that media companies must adapt their content to reach both audiences effectively. Younger viewers are more attracted to quick, engaging content, so news organisations use short videos, interactive posts, and social media updates to capture their attention. Platforms like TikTok, Instagram, and YouTube have become popular sources of news and entertainment for younger audiences. On the other hand, older people are more comfortable with traditional formats, such as newspapers, television news, and radio broadcasts, as they are familiar and easy to access. To balance both preferences, media companies now provide news in multiple formats. For example, some news agency report a major event on TV and in newspapers while also sharing a summarised version through social media platforms. Additionally, some traditional media outlets have developed websites and mobile apps to bridge the gap, allowing older audiences to slowly adapt to digital media while still providing younger viewers with the fast-paced content they prefer (Ofcom, 2020).

A person's income level also affects the type of media they use. Livingstone & Helsper (2007) argue that people with higher incomes have better access to digital media because they can afford smartphones, tablets and high-speed internet. On the other hand, those with lower incomes often rely more on free television and radio. This difference means that media companies need to find ways to reach both rich and poor audiences. Social media has also changed the way people consume media. Platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram have become major sources of news and entertainment. Many people now get their news from social media rather than from newspapers or television. However, social media has also raised concerns about misinformation and privacy. As a result of this, traditional media companies now use social media to share their content and stay relevant (Newman *et al* 2021).

Pariser (2011) avers that another important factor is personalised content. Many streaming services and news websites use special computer programs to recommend content based on what users like. This makes media more engaging, but it also creates "filter bubbles," where people only see content that matches their interests and opinions. This can lead to biased views and limited exposure to different perspectives. Hence the need for media literacy, which is important in helping people understand and think critically about the information they receive. There is no gainsaying that people consume the media differently. In Oredo Local Government area of Edo State, it can be deduced

that the residents consume the media for different reasons (to be informed, educated or entertained) and they have certain preferences. With the availability of both traditional and digital media, residents have developed certain preferences for different media formats depending on factors such as age, accessibility, and content relevance. Given the significance of media as a primary source of information and entertainment, it is essential to understand how residents of Oredo Local Government engage with different media platforms. The shift from traditional to digital media has created challenges for both media companies and audiences. Digital media is fast, easy to access, and allows people to get news and entertainment anytime. However, traditional media like newspapers, radio, and television are struggling to keep up. Many newspapers have shut down, radio stations have lost listeners, and fewer people watch television. Another issue is that different people consume media in different ways. Factors like age, income, and culture affect the type of media people prefer. Young people mostly use digital platforms like social media and streaming services, while older people still rely on newspapers, television, and radio. However, not much research has been done to understand how these differences affect media consumption, most especially at the local level. It is difficult to determine the media preference of the residents and the underlying factors behind their media choices; thus, this study sought to find out the differences in media consumption among residents of Oredo Local Government area of Edo State.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Examine the preferred types of media among residents of Oredo Local Government.
2. Analyse the factors influencing media consumption choices among residents of Oredo Local Government.
3. Identify the attitude of residents in Oredo Local Government towards traditional and digital media consumption.

Theoretical Framework

The researchers adopted the uses and gratifications theory as its theoretical framework. The uses and gratifications theory was developed by Elihu Katz, Jay G. Blumler & Michael Gurevitch in 1973. It focuses on why and how people actively seek out specific media to satisfy their needs. Unlike older theories that viewed media audiences as passive consumers, uses and gratifications sees them as active participants who make conscious choices based on personal needs, preferences, and expectations. The theory suggests that people consume media to fulfill specific desires such as information, entertainment, personal identity, and social interaction. The tenets of the theory include:

- People actively choose media based on their needs.
- Media consumption is intentional and based on certain gratifications.

- Different individuals use media for different reasons (e.g., to stay informed, relax or connect with others).
- Traditional and digital media compete to satisfy audience needs.
- People interpret media content in different ways depending on their experiences, beliefs, and environment.

The uses and gratifications theory is appropriate for this study because it focuses on media differences in media consumption among residents of Oredo Local Government, Edo State. The uses and gratifications theory is suitable because it explains how individuals actively choose between traditional and digital media based on their needs and preferences. Since the study explores how factors like age, culture, and income influence media consumption, this theory helps in understanding why different groups prefer certain media platforms over others. The uses and gratifications theory is relevant to this study because it helps explain why some residents of Oredo prefer newspapers, while others rely on social media or online news. It also helps media organisations create content that suits different groups based on their needs and preferences. Since people's attitudes influence their media choices, this theory provides insight into how personal needs shape media consumption. Additionally, it helps to understand why some individuals still prefer traditional media, while others have switched to digital platforms. By using this theory, the study can effectively assess the differences in media consumption among Oredo residents and how these differences affect their attitudes and preferences.

Concept of Media Consumption

Media consumption is the way people choose, engage with, and take in information from different media sources like television, radio, newspapers, the internet and social media (Dominick, 2013). It includes both old and new forms of media, meaning people can get information from printed newspapers or digital news websites, listen to the radio or stream podcasts, and watch television or online videos. The type of media people consume influences what they know, how they see the world, and what they find entertaining. For example, someone who regularly watches news channels may be more aware of current events, while another person who follows social media trends may be more interested in entertainment and lifestyle content. Statistica (2022) states that the rise of digital media has made it easier for people to access information anytime and anywhere, but it has also created differences in how people interact with media. Some actively engage by commenting and sharing, while others passively absorb information without participating. Regardless of the medium, media consumption plays an important role in shaping people's daily experiences and opinions.

Potter (2021) explains that media consumption is the process of accessing, using, and understanding content from various media sources, including television, radio, newspapers, social media and online platforms. It involves how people interact with media for different purposes, such as staying informed, seeking entertainment,

communicating with others and engaging in social interactions. The way individuals consume media can shape their opinions, influence their behaviours and affect their daily routines. Livingstone & Helsper (2007) point out that there are two main types of media consumption: active and passive.

Active media consumption happens when people engage directly with the content rather than just watching or listening. This includes actions like commenting on social media posts, sharing videos, participating in online discussions or even creating their own content, such as blogs, vlogs, or podcasts. Active consumers are more involved because they interact with what they are watching, reading, or listening to. On the other hand, passive media consumption happens when people simply watch, read, or listen to content without responding or interacting with it. This includes watching television, listening to the radio, or reading a newspaper without discussing it or engaging in any way. Passive consumers absorb information without taking any action. For instance, a person might listen to a morning radio show while driving to work without paying full attention or discussing what they heard.

Factors Affecting Media Differences in Media Consumption

People's choices of media depend on factors like their age, gender, job, and cultural background (Hora, 2022). Younger people use digital media such as social media and streaming platforms, while older people prefer traditional media like newspapers, radio, and television. Personal interests also play a role; for example, sports fans may choose TV channels or online platforms that offer live sports coverage, while news lovers may prefer newspapers or online news websites.

Asemah (2019) explains that culture strongly influences media preferences. People tend to consume media that aligns with their traditions, beliefs, and values. For example, some communities prefer local news channels or newspapers that discuss regional issues, while others engage with digital platforms that offer diverse global content. Additionally, religious beliefs affect media choices. People who follow a particular faith may prefer religious TV channels, radio stations or online content that supports their spiritual beliefs. IProject (2020) states that entertainment is another major factor in media consumption. Many people choose media based on how enjoyable it is. Those who love music may prefer radio stations or streaming services, while movie fans may spend more time on digital platforms like Netflix. The quality of content also matters. A well-edited news broadcast, a well-written newspaper article or a high-quality online video attracts more viewers. People are more likely to engage with media that creates an emotional connection and provides an enjoyable experience.

Finally, social interaction and community connection play a significant role in influencing differences in media consumption. People tend to choose media that helps them stay connected with their community and engage socially. Traditional media like newspapers and radio are preferred by those who value local news and community updates, as these platforms provide reliable information about their immediate

environment. On the other hand, social media and digital platforms appeal more to younger audiences because they allow for instant communication, real-time discussions and sharing of opinions. Additionally, media that promotes local talent, cultural identity and social causes tends to attract a loyal audience who feel a sense of belonging, (McCleish, 2015).

Effect of Media Differences in Media Consumption

Differences in media consumption can have several negative effects on individuals and society. When people rely too much on a particular type of media, whether traditional or digital, it can affect their engagement, understanding, and experience with information and entertainment. Ezeh (2020) outlined the following as the effect of media difference in media consumption:

a. **Reduced Attention Span:** People who frequently consume digital media, such as social media and online videos, may find it difficult to focus on long-form content like newspapers or television news. The habit of constantly switching between different media sources can make it harder for them to concentrate and absorb important information. This can lead to a shallow understanding of topics and reduced critical thinking skills.

b. **Cognitive overload:** When individuals are exposed to multiple media sources at once, their brains can become overwhelmed. For example, someone who watches television while scrolling through social media may struggle to process both forms of content effectively. This overload can make it harder to remember important details, follow a storyline or fully engage with information. In some cases, people may rely on short, simplified content from social media rather than taking the time to read in-depth news reports, which can lead to misinformation or a lack of deep knowledge on important issues.

c. **Physical Health:** People who spend too much time consuming digital media, such as watching online videos or using social media, tend to have more sedentary lifestyles. Sitting for long hours without physical activity can increase the risk of obesity, heart disease and other health problems. In addition, excessive screen time, especially at night, can interfere with sleep patterns, leading to tiredness and reduced focus the next day. On the other hand, traditional media, such as newspapers and radio encourage more physical movement, as people may walk to buy a newspaper or listen to the radio while doing other activities.

d. **Another Issue is Social Isolation.** Digital media allows people to connect online, but it can also reduce face-to-face interactions. Some individuals prefer chatting through messages or engaging in online discussions rather than having real conversations with

those around them. This can weaken personal relationships and lead to feelings of loneliness. On the other hand, traditional media, such as watching television with family or listening to the radio in a group, can create shared experiences that strengthen social bonds.

Empirical Review

Okoro & Nwafor (2013) examined "Social Media and Political Participation in Nigeria." This study aimed to examine how social media influence political participation among Nigerians. The researchers used a survey method, distributing questionnaire to students in select Nigerian universities to understand their engagement with political content on social media. The findings showed that social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter played a significant role in encouraging political discussions, raising awareness and mobilising young people for political activities. The researchers concluded that social media have become a powerful tool for political engagement, providing Nigerians with a space to express their opinions, interact with political leaders, and participate in national discussions. While this reviewed study focused on what people use the social media for, this study looked at the choice for media consumption. Both studies have different geographical scope.

Ezeh (2020) investigated Traditional vs Digital Media: A Study on News Consumption Patterns in Lagos. The study aimed to compare how people in Lagos consume news through traditional media (newspapers, radio and television) and digital media (social media, blogs and news websites). The researcher used a mixed-method approach, combining surveys and interviews to gather data from different age groups and professions. The findings revealed that younger audiences preferred digital media due to its speed and accessibility, while older audiences still relied on newspapers and television for credibility and detailed reports. The study concluded that while digital media is growing rapidly, traditional media remains relevant, especially for audiences who value in-depth analysis and reliability in news reporting. While this reviewed study show similarity with the current study in terms of consumption, they differ in terms of scope and method; however, they provide insight to the motivation for selecting different media for consumption

Methodology

The researchers employed a descriptive survey research design to gather data. A total of 384 copies of questionnaire were directly distributed to residents of Oredo Local Government Area, which has an estimated population of 553,300, as reported by the National Population Commission (2024). The sample was derived using Australian sample size calculator. Respondents were selected based on the systematic sampling technique. First, the researchers purposively selected the dominant roads in the Local government, then, the systematic random sampling technique was used to pick the 10th house in each road and the instrument was administered in such houses until saturation

point was reached. The collected data were organised into tables and analysed using percentages and frequency distributions. A mean benchmark of 2.50 was used to determine whether respondents agreed or disagreed with each statement in the questionnaire.

Data Presentation and Analysis

A total of 384 copies of questionnaire were distributed, 359 were returned and found usable. The data generated from the questionnaire collected are presented and analysed below:

Table1: Preferred Types of Media among Residents of Oredo Local Government

Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
I prefer digital media (e.g., social media, online news) over traditional media (e.g., newspapers, radio, TV).	264	60	28	0	3.48	Agree
I prefer listening to the radio rather than watching television for news and entertainment.	220	111	20	8	3.59	Agree
I frequently consume news and entertainment through social media platforms.	180	90	30	10	3.10	Agree
Average mean					3.39	Agree

Source: Field Survey 2025

Based on the data in table 1, it is evident that residents of Oredo Local Government have a strong preference for both digital and traditional media, depending on their specific media needs. The findings show that a significant number of residents prefer digital media, such as social media and online news, over traditional media, with a mean score of 3.48. This indicates that digital platforms are becoming a popular source of information and entertainment. However, the data also reveal that radio remains a highly preferred medium, with the highest mean score of 3.59. This shows that many residents still rely on radio for news and entertainment, possibly due to its accessibility and convenience.

Additionally, the study highlights that social media are frequently used for news and entertainment, as reflected in a mean score of 3.10. This demonstrates the increasing role of social media in shaping media consumption habits. With an overall average mean of 3.39, the findings confirm that while digital media is widely embraced, traditional media still holds significant importance among residents. This implies that media consumption in Oredo Local Government is diverse, with people balancing both digital and traditional platforms based on their preferences and accessibility.

Table 2: Factors influencing Media Consumption Choices among Residents of Oredo Local Government

Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
My choice of media is influenced by the affordability of internet access.	184	90	40	4	3.18	Agree
I choose my media source based on how quickly it provides updates on current event	156	13	22	3	3.16	Agree
The credibility and trustworthiness of a media platform influence my media consumption decisions.	220	13	0	0	3.55	Agree
Average mean		5			3.30	Agree

Based on the data in table 2, it is clear that several key factors influence the media consumption choices of residents in Oredo Local Government. The findings reveal that affordability of internet access plays a significant role, with a mean score of 3.18. This indicates that residents are more likely to engage with digital media when they have access to affordable internet, making cost an important consideration in their media choices. Additionally, the speed of updates on current events is another major factor, with a mean score of 3.16. This indicates that residents prefer media sources that provide timely and up-to-date news, reinforcing the appeal of fast-paced digital platforms.

Furthermore, credibility and trustworthiness appear to be the strongest influencing factor, with the highest mean score of 3.55. This shows that residents prioritise reliable information when selecting their media sources, regardless of whether it is traditional or digital. With an overall average mean of 3.30, the findings confirm that affordability, speed of updates, and trustworthiness are the primary factors shaping media consumption habits in Oredo Local Government. This highlights the importance of accessible and credible media platforms in ensuring informed and engaged audiences.

Table 3: Attitude of Residents in Oredo Local Government towards traditional and Digital Media Consumption

Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
I trust traditional media more than digital media when it comes to news accuracy.	112	216	0	0	3.28	Agree
I believe newspapers and radio are becoming less relevant in today's society.	108	165	20	8	2.81	Agree
I feel comfortable relying on social media as my main news source.	120	84	60	12	2.76	Agree
Average mean					2.95	Agree

Based on the data in table 3, it is evident that residents of Oredo Local Government have a mixed, but generally positive attitude toward traditional and digital media consumption.

The findings indicate that most residents still trust traditional media for news accuracy, with a mean score of 3.28. This shows that newspapers, radio, and television continue to hold credibility among the people. However, there is also a notable perception that traditional media is becoming less relevant in modern society, as reflected in the mean score of 2.81. This implies that while residents acknowledge the reliability of traditional media, they also recognise the growing dominance of digital platforms.

Furthermore, the study reveals that a significant number of residents feel comfortable relying on social media as their main news source, with a mean score of 2.76. This highlights the increasing influence of digital media in shaping news consumption habits. With an overall average mean of 2.95, the results confirm that residents of Oredo Local Government have an evolving attitude toward media consumption. While they still value traditional media for accuracy, they are gradually adapting to digital platforms, signaling a shift in media preference over time.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into media differences in media consumption patterns among residents in Oredo Local Government, Edo State. Based on the data presented and analysed, the results from table 1 indicate a strong preference for both digital and traditional media, depending on the specific media needs of residents. The data show that many residents prefer digital media, such as social media and online news, over traditional platforms with a mean score of 3.48. This trend aligns with global shifts in media consumption, where digital platforms provide instant access to news and entertainment. However, radio remains a popular choice with a mean score of 3.59, indicating that it still holds relevance due to its accessibility, affordability, and ease of use, especially among those who may not have constant internet access. Additionally, frequent social media use for news and entertainment (Mean score of 3.10) highlights how digital platforms are shaping modern media habits. These findings are consistent with Newman *et al* (2022) which indicated that digital media consumption is on the rise, while traditional media continues to serve key functions among certain demographics.

The findings from table 2 show that affordability, speed of news updates and credibility significantly influence media consumption choices among residents. Affordability of internet access is a major factor with a Mean score of 3.18. This indicates that economic considerations shape how people engage with digital media. The findings also indicate that another key factor is the speed of news updates. With mean score of 3.16, the findings show that residents are drawn to platforms that offer real-time news and instant updates, a strength of digital and social media. This preference highlights the growing demand for fast and on-the-go information consumption, which aligns with findings from past studies on news consumption trends. However, the strongest influencing factor is credibility and trustworthiness (Mean score of 3.55).

This shows that regardless of the platform, residents prioritise media sources they perceive as reliable. This finding is consistent with Wardle & Derakhsan's (2017)

research which shows that media consumers often cross-check news sources to verify information, especially in an era of misinformation and fake news. The overall average mean (3.30) confirms that economic, technological, and trust-based factors collectively determine how people consume media in Oredo Local Government.

The findings from table 3 reveal a mixed but evolving attitude toward media consumption. While residents still trust traditional media for news accuracy (with a mean score of 3.28), there is a growing perception that newspapers and radio are becoming less relevant in today's society. This shows that while traditional media retains credibility, its influence is gradually declining due to the rise of digital alternatives. Furthermore, the data indicate that many residents feel comfortable relying on social media as their main news source with a mean score of 2.76. This highlights the growing role of social platforms in news consumption, despite concerns about misinformation. The findings align with the Uses and Gratifications Theory (Blumler & Katz, 1974), which holds that individuals choose media based on their needs, whether for credibility, speed or accessibility. The overall mean of 2.95 shows that while traditional media remains respected for accuracy, residents are adapting to digital media for convenience and immediacy. This shift aligns with global trends where digital platforms continue to redefine how people access and interact with information.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the study shows that while more people are choosing digital media, traditional media, especially radio, is still important because it is easy to access and trusted. The main factors that affect people's media choices are the cost of internet access, how quickly news is updated, and how trustworthy a media source is. Although, many residents still believe traditional media provides more accurate news, there is a slow shift towards digital platforms, especially social media, for news and entertainment. Based on the findings, it is concluded that people in Oredo Local Government use both traditional and digital media, depending on what is more convenient, affordable, and reliable for them. In line with the findings, the following are suggested;

1. Radio stations in Benin City should continue to create programmes that sustain public interest in order to retain its high level of consumption.
2. Mainstream media who are yet to digital their content do set an immediate plan in place to digitalise their content
3. Digital news sources should set fact checking softwares in order to gain public trust on credibility.

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